

**MULTIPLE GRAPHIC ORGANIZERS AS TOOLS IN ENHANCING
THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 11 STUDENTS
IN PHILIPPINE POLITICS AND GOVERNANCE**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11215235>

ABSTRACT

This study sought to determine the effectiveness of multiple graphic organizers as tools in enhancing the academic performance of grade 11 students in Philippine Politics and Governance. This study utilized experimental-descriptive research and used teacher-made test as main data gathering instrument. The study was conducted at Callejon National High School during the first quarter of the school year 2018-2019 with 51 Grade 11 respondents chosen purposively. The following statistical tools were used: mean, percentage, standard deviation, Pearson-r and F-test. The study found out that the respondents are in the right age in their respective grade. In terms of gender, the female outnumbered male respondents. As to the perception in the use of multiple graphic organizers, all falls under the description of “agree/high extent”. Meanwhile, post-test scores revealed that their skill performance got a rating of 85-89%. Furthermore, there is no significant difference in the post-test score in understanding and comprehension skills when tested to $p < .05$. Correlation between the perceived use of multiple graphic organizers and students’ performance revealed that concept map graphic organizer and comprehension are significantly related. Likewise, compare and contrast graphic organizer is also significantly related to understanding. The result shows that the utilization of graphic organizers in Philippine Politics and Governance helps the students in organizing material, recognizing the key concepts, and focus on the important information in the topic. Through this study, administrators may provide teachers with more training and seminars on the new and innovative teaching instructions.

Keywords: *Multiple Graphic Organizer, Academic Performance, Philippine Politics and Governance, Purposive, Significant*

INTRODUCTION

“I’m not satisfied until my students fall in love with history. The key is to set up things, so they discover history”.

–David Mc Cullough, Historian and Professor at Cornell University.

As part of the education reform agenda of the government, the K to 12 Basic Education Program provides the foundation by which every child begins to define him/herself. Since its approval in 2013, the curriculum has created changes in the way high school students are trained that may not only equip them to the world of work, entrepreneurship or prepare themselves for higher learning but for possible employment as well.

In connection, a teacher plays a vital role within a few hours in the classroom by delivering the daily specific planned content which is a part of curriculum for a specific grade. It depends on the teacher to plan it out and use effective strategies for its instructional deliverance. Teachers must have passion for learning and teaching as well as to understand the needs and interests of the students. The world is changing and advancing day by day, so teachers need to be more innovative to meet new global emerging demands in education whose goal is to produce globally competitive individuals that will promote innovation and progress.

The social science subjects being offered to senior high school encompass diverse concerns of society and include a wide range of content, drawn from the disciplines of history, geography, political science, economics, and sociology (Singh, 2018). Philippine Politics and Governance is one of the specialized subjects under the Academic Strand and the HUMSS Strand being undertaken by the students to enable them to develop a brilliant mind to understand the importance and beauty of political science.

Therefore, thinking is a necessary skill needed in an educational setting at present, thus, there are different strategies and approaches available for teachers to impart the skill to the students. As a matter of fact, educators are very heedful in their pursuit of a new concept to promote effective learning and thinking skills (Hernandez, 2010). Changing teachers’ concepts and the impact on instructions are difficult and complex phenomenon. One step towards this is to provide experiences where these concepts will be challenged, and teachers will have opportunities to reflect on and look on the other ways where students’ participation on the teaching and learning process will be maximized.

Graphic organizers are simple tools utilized by students to help them grasp key information and the students also scored better when graphic organizer was used in teaching reading (Trinh Thi Ha My (Mary), 2012). In addition, Stowe (2015) stated that using graphic organizers is an excellent teaching strategy in many ways. It helps the students to comprehend, arrange, and remember new concepts by putting these concepts into practice.

Thus, graphic organizers are effective tools to use in teaching social science subjects. With the use of graphic organizer, the students can organize and communicate information in a visual way, and it might help them to make content areas accessible to them.

The researcher, as Senior High School Social Science teacher in a public secondary school in the district of San Antonio, Division of Quezon, teaching Philippine Politics and Governance as one of the specialized subjects of Grade 11 students under General Academic Strand (GAS) deemed it is important to help address the concern of every school head and teacher to improve the performance of the students in Social Science. The researcher is of the idea that students' academic performance will be enhanced with the use of multiple graphic organizers as instructional tools. These multiple graphic organizers could be one of the answers on how to develop the thinking skills of the learners and help them focus on the important information within the text to promote effective learning. These aids have a big impact for a student to be a more proactive participant in a life-long learning process. It also provides the necessary framework for students to complete a task meaningfully by helping them to categorize, infer, summarize, compare and contrast, evaluate, and so much more.

Moreover, educational reforms may address the present status of Social Studies instruction, especially the performance of fourth year students in the Division of Quezon province in the National Achievement Test during the school year 2014-2015. Callejon National High School has Social Studies MPS of 42.53 %. Philippine Politics and Governance subject got an MPS of 56. 19 % as the lowest MPS score in all subjects of Grade 11 General Academic Strand students in the school year 2017-2018. The data reveals that the results of the MPS seem abreast of the standard passing rate which is 75%. It also shows that students find it difficult to understand the basic concepts and vital elements of politics and governance that helps them gain a better appreciation of their rights and responsibilities as individuals and as members of the larger sociopolitical community to strengthen their civic competence. It also shows that many important things must be done to improve the academic performance of the students.

In this case, the teachers continuously improve and innovates their teaching strategies and instruction to meet the diversified needs of the learners and make sure that students are effectively progressing based on assessments to meet the demands of the globally competitive graduates.

The researcher wished to figure out the effectiveness of multiple graphic organizers in Philippine Politics and Governance subject by assessing the class in Grade 11. The section underwent instruction using graphic organizers as strategy.

The researcher, being a member of this school chose the mentioned research to help in the promotion of quality education and provide all potential help in planning and implementation of academic programs of the school for whatever possible help this study may bring.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of?
 - 1.1 age and
 - 1.2 gender?
2. What is the level of respondents' agreement on the perception of using Multiple Graphic Organizers in Philippine Politics and Governance as to:
 - 2.1 concept map;
 - 2.2 cause and effect; and
 - 2.3 compare and contrast?
3. What is the performance of Grade 11 students using Multiple Graphic Organizers in terms of the following skills:
 - 3.1 understanding;
 - 3.2 comprehension; and
 - 3.3 remembering?
4. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the students using Multiple Graphic Organizers in terms of the following skills:
 - 4.1 understanding;
 - 4.2 comprehension; and
 - 4.3 remembering?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the perception of the respondents on the use of multiple graphic organizers and students' performance?

Hypotheses:

After careful study the following hypothesis are considered:

1. There is no significant difference in the performance of the respondents using multiple graphic organizers in terms of:
 - 1.1 understanding;
 - 1.2 comprehension and
 - 1.3 remembering?
2. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' use of multiple graphic organizers and their performance.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at Callejon National High School during the first quarter of the school year 2018-2019 with 51 Grade 11 respondents chosen purposively. The following statistical tools were used: mean, percentage, standard deviation, Pearson-r and F-test.

The data were gathered using a researcher's made test in chosen topic in Philippine Politics and Governance. A teacher-made test composed of 45 items for all the selected topics discussed in the First Quarter. In addition, a self-made survey

questionnaire was also be made to obtain the perception of the respondents in the utilization of graphic organizers.

The following steps were followed in the construction and validation of teacher-made test and the self-made survey questionnaire. First, content validation, the researcher constructed a table of specification based on the objectives of the lessons before the construction of the test items and survey questionnaire. It included the selected topics of the researcher made instruction. Second, face validation, the test items, and the indicators to be used in survey questionnaire were inspected and evaluated by the research adviser, schools' principal, master teacher and one of the Social Studies teachers at the school where the researcher conducted the study for comments and suggestions. It was also reviewed by an editor for necessary corrections on the clarity of directions, language used, correct usage of grammar and content. Necessary corrections were made, suitable items retained, and some items were modified and revised. Third, trial run, the validated test and survey questionnaire were administered to TVL-Home Economics students. The researcher constructed a post-test with 45 items as an instrument to be used in Philippine Politics and Governance subject. The result was subjected to item analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	f	%
Male	24	47.06
Female	27	52.94
Total	51	100.00

Table 2. Distribution of Respondents by Age

Age	f	%
18-above	14	27.45
16-18	37	72.55
13-15	-	-
Total	51	100.00

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	f	%
Male	24	47.06
Female	27	52.94
Total	51	100.00

Table 4. Respondents' Perception on the Use of Concept Map Graphic Organizer

	Indicators <i>Concept Map Graphic Organizer helps me...</i>	\bar{x}	sd	Interpretation
1.	Brainstorm and generate new ideas.	4.10	0.78	Agree / High Extent
2.	Understand how different subtopics relate to the main topic.	4.04	0.77	Agree / High Extent
3.	Encourage to discover new concepts and the prepositions that connects them.	3.94	0.73	Agree / High Extent
4.	Communicate ideas, thoughts, and information.	4.10	0.73	Agree / High Extent
5.	Integrate new concepts with older concepts.	3.84	0.70	Agree / High Extent
6.	Enhanced knowledge of any topic and evaluate the information.	3.98	0.81	Agree / High Extent
7.	Visually illustrates the relationships between concepts and ideas.	4.14	0.78	Agree / High Extent
	Over-all	4.02	0.47	Agree / High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00: Strongly Agree/Very High Extent 3.41-4.20: Agree/ High Extent 2.61-3.40: Moderately Agree/Moderately Extent 1.81-2.60: Disagree/Low Extent 1.00-1.80: Strongly Disagree/Not at All

Table 5. Respondents' Perception on the Use of Cause and Effect Graphic Organizer

	Indicators <i>Cause and Effect Graphic Organizer helps me...</i>	\bar{x}	sd	Interpretation
1.	Find out the causes and effect pattern in text.	4.25	0.74	Strongly Agree/ Very High extent
2.	Show the problem solving process.	4.18	0.71	Agree / High Extent
3.	Identify a problem and various solutions tried.	4.02	0.79	Agree / High Extent
4.	Think about complex cause-and-effect relationships.	4.10	0.73	Agree / High Extent
5.	Consider multiple causes of events.	4.00	0.77	Agree / High Extent
6.	Visualize the various cause and effect relationships clearly.	4.10	0.81	Agree / High Extent
7.	Taking notes based on text and videos.	3.94	0.90	Agree / High Extent
	Over-all	4.08	0.53	Agree/ High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00: Strongly Agree/Very High Extent 3.41-4.20: Agree/ High Extent 2.61-3.40: Moderately Agree/Moderately Extent 1.81-2.60: Disagree/Low Extent 1.00-1.80: Strongly Disagree/Not at All

Table 6. Respondents' Perceptions on the Use of Compare and Contrast Graphic Organizer

	Indicators <i>Compare and Contrast Graphic Organizer helps me...</i>	\bar{x}	sd	Interpretation
1.	Visualize similarities and differences between two things.	4.35	0.72	Strongly Agree/ Very High Extent
2.	Check my comprehension.	4.00	0.66	Agree/High Extent
3.	Challenge my capacity to think and analyze.	4.20	0.75	Agree/High Extent
4.	Condense and organize data about multiple traits.	3.82	0.71	Agree/High Extent
5.	Evaluate information.	4.16	0.78	Agree/High Extent
6.	Engage in deep thinking in comparing two concepts.	4.10	0.73	Agree/High Extent
	Over-all	4.10	0.51	Agree/High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00: Strongly Agree/Very High Extent 3.41-4.20: Agree/ High Extent 2.61-3.40: Moderately Agree/Moderately Extent 1.81-2.60: Disagree/Low Extent 1.00-1.80: Strongly Disagree/Not at All

Table 7. Summary of the Respondents' Perception in the Use of Multiple Graphic Organizers in Philippine Politics and Governance

Graphic Organizers	\bar{x}	sd	Interpretation
Concept Map	4.02	0.47	Agree / High Extent
Cause and Effect	4.08	0.53	Agree / High Extent
Compare and Contrast	4.10	0.51	Agree / High Extent
Over-all	4.07	0.50	Agree / High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00: Strongly Agree/Very High Extent 3.41-4.20: Agree/ High Extent 2.61-3.40: Moderately Agree/Moderately Extent 1.81-2.60: Disagree/Low Extent 1.00-1.80: Strongly Disagree/Not at All

Table 8. Skill Performance of Grade 11 Students in Philippine Politics and Governance

Rating	Scores	Understanding		Comprehension		Remembering		Interpretation
		F	%	f	%	f	%	
90-above	13-15	13	25.49	15	29.41	14	27.45	Excellent
85-89	10-12	20	39.22	16	31.37	5	9.8	Very Good
80-84	7-9	12	23.53	14	27.45	11	21.57	Good
75-79	4-6	6	11.76	6	11.76	13	25.49	Fair
70-74	0-3	-	-	-	-	8	15.69	Poor
	Total	51	100	51	100	51	100	

Table 9. Test of Difference (ANOVA) in the Performance of the Students using Multiple Graphic Organizers

Variables		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F value	P Value	Remarks
Understanding	Between groups	1070.588	535.294	10.379	.000	Significant
	Within groups	7736.471	51.576	-	-	-
	Total	8807.059	-	-	-	-
Comprehension	Between groups	655.529	327.765	4.982	.008	Significant
	Within groups	9868.235	65.788	-	-	-
	Total	10523.765	-	-	-	-
Remembering	Between groups	7.529	3.765	.053	.948	Not Significant
	Within groups	10606.588	70.711	-	-	-
	Total	10614.118	-	-	-	-

Legend: $p > .05$ not significant, $p < .05$ significant

Table 10. Correlation between the Perceived use of Multiple Graphic Organizers and Students Performance

Variables	Understanding	Comprehension	Remembering
Concept Map	.238	.281*	.149
Cause and Effect	.130	.073	.003
Compare and Contrast	.353*	.221	.048

Legend: r value is significant at **.01, at *.05

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows distribution of respondents as to gender. It shows that most of the respondents are female 27.

Table 2 presents distribution of respondents as to age. It shows that the greatest number of respondents is 16-18 years old with about 72.55 % of the total respondents (51), meaning they are in the right age in their respective grade levels.

Table 3 shows the distribution of respondents as to gender. The data shows that the female respondents comprise 52.94 % of the total respondents while male respondents is about 47.06 %. This means that the female respondents outnumbered the male respondents by 5.88 %.

Table 4 shows the perception of the respondents in the use of concept map graphic organizer. It reveals that most of the respondents “agreed” in all indicators. Item no. 7 “visually illustrates the relationships between concept and ideas” got the highest mean score of 4.14. However, indicator no. 5 “Integrate new concepts with older concepts got the lowest mean score of 3.84 and standard deviation of 0.70. Concept map graphic organizer gained an over-all mean score of 4.02; SD=0.47 which is agree/ high extent.

The data in Table 4 also implies that concept map graphic organizer helps the learners in enhancing their knowledge and evaluating the information.

Empirically, the result in this table agrees with the findings of the study of Myers and Savage (2005) that graphic organizers promote comprehension and aids in student learning with the complex content often addressed in social studies.

Table 5 shows that respondents have a common agreement in the use of cause-and-effect graphic organizer. It can be gleaned from the table that Items No. 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 have a mean score of 4.18 to 3.94 which are interpreted as “agree”/” high extent.” The table also reveals that only item no. 1 having a mean score of 4.25; SD=0.074 falls

on “strongly agree”/” very high extent”. The respondents agree/high extent with the use of cause-and-effect graphic organizers with an over-all mean of 4.08.

Both concept mapping and cause and effect graphic organizers were found being utilized to a “high extent”.

The findings imply that students may find learning more appealing by using cause and effect graphic organizers and it sustained their level of interest in a particular topic in Philippine Politics and Governance.

Table 6 shows the strength of the use of compare and contrast graphic organizers. It shows that the learners can visualize similarities and differences between two things. This is seen in indicator 1 having a mean score of 4.35, SD=0.72 which is “strongly agree”/” very high extent”.

In like manner, item numbers 2 to 6 falls in between the scores 4.20 to 3.82 respectively which were interpreted as “agree”/ high extent”. Cause and Effect organizer got an over-all mean of 4.10 with standard deviation of 0.51 which is “agree”/” high extent”.

Stowe (2015) stated that using graphic organizers is an excellent teaching strategy in many ways. It helps the students to comprehend, arrange, and remember new concepts by putting these concepts into practice.

Generally, graphic organizers are beneficial in teaching and learning. It makes the study interesting and efficient by showing relationships, visualizing and simplifying ideas, and organizing information in texts.

Table 7 presents the summary of the respondents’ perceptions in using multiple graphic organizers in Philippine Politics and Governance. It is manifested in the data above, that all types of graphic organizers got verbal interpretation of “agree”/” high extent”, (M=4.07, SD=0.50). The result also implies that respondents perceived graphic organizers as useful teaching tools that help them better understood the lessons actively involved in the different activities.

The result is supported by the study of Hernandez (2010) who suggested that the teacher may develop an instructional material like graphic organizer in other subjects as tool in understanding the different concepts in facilitating self-learning and develop thinking skills of the students. The study also shows that graphic organizers contribute to better test scores in social studies context because it helps students understand the key relationships and ideas of the curriculum thus enabling them to be more focused in their study.

As seen in Table 8, as to skills in understanding, out of 51 students 20 among them got a score of 10-12 with a rating of 85-89 which is interpreted as “very good”. It is also observed that none of them got 0-3 with 70-74 in rating. While in comprehension, 16 out of 51 students got scores of 10-12 which is equivalent to a rating of 85-89; fifteen (15) of them got a rating of 90 –above which is interpreted as “excellent” and fourteen (14) falls

under 80-84 which is interpreted as “good “. None of them failed in the said skill. However, in remembering skill eight (8) of them failed maybe because answers to questions were all names of persons, places or things and they found difficulty in remembering them. Nevertheless, fourteen (14) of them got a rating of 90 and above.

Analyzing the results in the table it can be inferred that students in Philippine Politics and Governance performed better with graphic organizers.

Table 9 shows that there is a significant difference in the performance of students in understanding using the three (3) graphic organizers namely concept map, cause and effect and compare and contrast.

The p - value of .000 corresponding to understanding signifies the difference. Empirically, it is noteworthy that the use of multiple graphic organizers affected also the performance of the students and so the teacher may also take it into consideration as the strategic way of applying types of graphic organizer. With the result, teacher in Philippine Politics and Governance can now discriminate which type of graphic organizer will be utilized more often. Similar situation can be manifested in comprehension.

The p - value of .008 signifies the significant difference in the comprehension skill of students using the three (3) graphic organizers seemingly, teacher in Philippine Politics and Governance may be sensitive in choosing the kind of graphic organizers he or she needs to apply.

Empirically, most of the skills performance of students are affected by the use of graphic organizer, thus it is found to be effective somehow. This finding is in consonant with the study of Baxendell (2003) which stated that graphic organizers have been shown to be effective in improving the understanding and application of content materials for students varying ability levels.

In addition, the study of Trinh Thi Ha My (Mary) (2012) found out that graphic organizers help increase the comprehension skills of the students. The result also showed that students scored better in post-test than in the pretest and the lessons which was used of graphic organizer in teaching reading for student is valid.

Both studies revealed the effectiveness of graphic organizers in enhancing the academic performance of the students. Thus, employing this as strategy or tools in discussing a lesson is beneficial to the students.

At the cursory look in Table 10 it was found out that compare and contrast has its significant relationship with understanding with an r - value of .353. Likewise, concept map also registered significant relationship with comprehension with an r – value of .281.

However, it is noteworthy that cause and effect has no significant relationship with the three (3) identified skills. So, the graphic organizer such as concept map and compare and contrast are considered effective. Maybe because the result could have been affected by the type of graphic organizers being enhanced since graphic organizers are

intended to show relationship, visualize, and simplify ideas, and organize information which all falls under understanding and comprehension level.

However, the result of the study found out that utilization of graphic organizers in Philippine Politics and Governance helps the students in organizing material, recognizing the key concepts, and focus on the important information in the topic.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The null hypothesis stating that “there is no significant difference in the performance of the respondents’ using multiple graphic organizers” is not sustained.
 2. The null hypothesis stating “that there is no significant relationship between the use of multiple graphic organizers and students’ performance” is not sustained.
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Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions posted in the study, the following recommendations are hereby formulated:

1. Through the findings of the study, administrators may provide teachers more trainings and seminars on the new and innovative teaching instruction which can address the increasing needs of different types of learners specifically on the use of graphic organizers so that teachers may develop a lesson which is congruent to the graphic organizers needed for the topic. Those graphic organizers may serve better tools for educators to measure the growth and assessing students’ progress.
2. The findings of the study may give insights to teachers in using different teaching instructions which can be effective in the teaching learning process. Teachers may develop a lesson with full utilization of the use of concept map graphic organizers

because students find it interesting to use during the lesson as it reiterates their ideas using their own words and helps identify incorrect ideas and concepts.

3. Future researchers may as well consider the use of multiple graphic organizers and incorporate them into their studies to further validate the findings of the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

For ethical considerations, the researcher asked the informants consent through written letter and verbal. The researcher assured the confidentiality and anonymity of their answers and details. Ethical approval of the study was given by the school principal.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express his sincere gratitude and deep appreciation to those who, in one way or another, have helped him in the preparation and completion of this study.

Dr. Eva F. Puyo and Dr. Nelia T. Salvador, for their expert advice, intellectual guidance and invaluable assistance rendered in making this work a reality;

Mr. Loreto De Chavez and Mrs. Lydia Magpantay Vasquez, his parents for the love and concern and bearing all the hardship in raising the researcher and his siblings and so for the words of encouragement. Thanks a lot;

Callejon National High School community for supporting the studies, for giving technical supports and for making the atmosphere light;

Co-teachers and dear friends, Jomar, Levi, Dennis, Uchie, Aizel, Arwin, Angelo, Donna Faye, Marvin, Morlan for their moral support during the completion of this study.

The unmentioned people, relatives, friends, colleagues and authors who have shared their resources, intellectual property, time, effort and support of all kinds;

Above all, to the Almighty God to whom he owes everything; for without Him, he is nothing.

-LMV

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